

"Comparing and environmental assessment of different structural systems in residential and industrial construction"

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to study an environmental assessment of different structural systems in residential and industrial construction buildings. Different structural systems in residential buildings are ubiquitous in world, It is the master structure for housing; however, due to the residential increase developments, developed of the different structural systems as wood, steel and reinforced concrete houses are also on the rise. This paper assesses the environmental effects of these three types of different construction. An assessments of the three types of different construction in terms of Carbon emissions ratio air emissions and used energy is done, that affecting the environment negatively. A comparison between types of structures, the disadvantage costs due to the turn out emissions is also considered. There four different types of emissions generated are evaluated, these are suspended particulate matter (SPM), carbon oxides emissions (CO₂) nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sulfur oxides (SO_x). Two different of the life cycle of the housing construction types is environmental and traced effects are determined. all costs are also calculated. Furthermore, there different improvement assessment ways are simulation to achieve it several emission de possibilities. The research looks into the emitted emissions from the housing construction to its final disposal of a typical residential development . Results and conclusions show that much of the environmental effects from building a house are on the Global Warming Potential due to high carbon emissions. Moreover, the construction phase generated the highest contaminated emissions from nitrogen oxides, sulfur oxides and suspended particulate matter. Steel reinforced concrete (SRC) construction has a higher environmental effects compared to the steel structures and wooden structures type of housing construction. A longer design life for a residential house gives a decrease of about 17% in carbon emissions. Using solar energy system for the operation stage has gained a decrease of 69% in the total carbon emissions for the life cycle.

Keywords: Residential and industrial construction, Environmental effects; Sustainable development, An environmental assessment

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1. Introduction

Steel reinforced concrete structures (SRCS) type comprises as a ratio about 45% of all residential construction buildings. Steel structures (SS) type comprises as a ratio about 15% of all residential construction buildings wooden structures (WS) type of housing is ubiquitous in world. It constitutes a ratio about 40% of all residential construction houses in world [1]. In recent years shows that there was increase in SRC type of separated houses compared to increase in wooden houses and increase in SRC type. Due to the increase in residential construction developments, SRC houses are also on the rise, therefore there is a need to assess the environmental effects of these three types of housing construction. Housing is one of the areas in urban development that needs to be assessed in conditions of its environmental effects. Housing is a very basic human need that stakeholders in residential construction development sometimes do not consider the effects of building such residential construction properties [2]. There is a need to evaluate the environmental effects of these housing developments; therefore, this paper will study the environmental effects of three types of the most common residential construction in the area. The three types of construction will be evaluated in conditions of energy usage and air emissions. Damage costs due to the generated emissions are also compared. The main purpose of the study is to compare the three types of residential construction, namely, Steel reinforced concrete structures, the steel structures type and wooden structures through its life cycle and assess different improvement scenarios that will lessen the environmental burden from these housing types. Four types of the emissions found are considered, that namely the carbon emissions (CO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulfur oxides (SO_x) and suspended particulate matter (SPM). The life cycle of the three different housing construction types will be traced and environmental effects considered [3]. A simulation of different improvement assessment scenarios is evaluated. The emissions from the three residential construction types can be traced from its construction, maintenance, operation and disposal of the houses. Life cycle analysis (LCA) is a methodology able to address this issue. LCA is a procedure to assess the sustainability of a product through consideration of all environmental implications of development, from primary inputs to disposal of final output and byproducts, including wastes. That respect, life cycle can be used to eco-balance assessment of the product. Several studies have been done to evaluate the environmental soundness of buildings and housing. [4] evaluated of the LC energy of a 50,000 ft² (4620 m²) three-story general office structure for alternative steel wood, and concrete structural systems in Canada. studied the total life cycle energy of a standard house in Michigan. They use typical LC methodology for evaluates embodied energy of the house. On the other hand [5], used the Eco Balance model to study the ecological effects of Eco villages and he indicated that eco-villages may not be very sound from an ecological point of view.

Examined the energy use in ten Florida developments built in the 1980s and they concluded that increased occupancy increases household energy use. They also mentioned that separated households consume substantially more electricity than attached households. assessed the environmental sustainability of multi-family estates in Korea. He evaluated and selected the housing sustainability of estates based on Korean standards and sustainability indicators [6,7] evaluated the embodied emissions of different types of housing construction and the materials used. They found out that main materials in new housing construction contribute to the increase in embodied CO₂ emissions. Literature review and studies did not compare between SRC, SS and WS also the total embodied emissions from three types of residential housing construction so this paper will study and try to investigate that issue.

Fig. 1. The sources of air pollution [WHO].

2. Assessment Methodology

(ISO) issued four related international standards in 1997 for Life Cycle Assessment practice. According to the standards of the fourth series of ISO 14040 standard LCA can be defined as "a method for abstracting and assessing the all investment of a product system in the all life cycle, and the influence or potential impact on the environment. Therefore, LCA can be considered as a methodology for estimating the environmental burdens of processes of production of services and goods during their LCA (e.g., from cradle to grave). According to ISO 14.040, LCA is contained of four different stages, which are:

- Scope and Goal definition. In this stage a motivations discussion, altogether with the depth and scope of the assessment, is performed in order to establish whole preliminary concerns relevant the LCA study.
- Analysis of Inventory . In involves collecting of data to all materials quantify, emissions and energy considered as inputs and outputs of the studied systems during its LCA.

- Effect Assessment. This phase is related to converting data recovered from the inventory into impacts and effects over the environment due to production of the systems assessed.

- Interpretation. The stage presents of the results and discussion obtained at the inventory or impact assessment phases, and contains conclusions and recommendations.

firstly, the environmental assessment's scope and goal are established, subsequently followed by the inventory analysis. That same pointed out in the ISO standard, the LC can be finished at this stage, provides a general of the direct effects generated by the assess systems; nevertheless, the assessments is pursued further, then an effect assessment is performed. It is very important to sure that, to both LCI and LCA researches; a sensitivity analysis of the assessment should be performed in order to identify errors or issues. Depending on the results and observations reached from this analysis, a revision view of the previous stages can be required. Finally, all the effects obtained from the LCA or LCI study, depending on the case, are summarized of the interpretation stage, which provides a general view of the research results and discussion.

3. An environmental assessment of steel reinforced concrete structures (SRC):-

Concrete construction industry is considers to be one of the very important economic sections worldwide, but at the same time, it is also one of the pollution emitting and resources. It is hold responsible for 300% of energy consumption in (OECD) countries[8] and according to other researches it is established that concrete constructions environmental effect in developed countries can be as high as 40%[9]. Concrete structures, with an estimated consumption of 6 million tons per year (what is the same as 1 ton per person/per year)[10], is considered the most world-wide concrete construction material used. for that, a better use of concrete structure is a related and challenge problem for concrete structure industry, that is already pointed to by 11]. In this issue, many of attempts to decrease environmental, economic and social effects due to concrete construction activities have already been made to this date. but it is a fact this, when considers the complete LS of a structure projects, influence of measures decreases as project progresses. wherefore, if improving continuities is a must of the construction industry, it is very necessary to provide decisions-makers with active tools to be applied at the initial stage of project's life cycle, the objective can be achieve by contain tools such as Life Cycle Assessment in the design, construction, demolition and operational stages of concrete structures.

Fig. 2. The cement sources of air pollution [WHO].

4. Life Cycle Assessment: Birth and Evolution

There researchers at the (MRI) began researching on a technique to quantifying energy resources and environmental emissions, that related to process of the manufacturing and use of byproducts[12]. Initially name “ Profile Analysis of Resource and Environmental ” (PARE), it was first applied in 1969 by America’s (MRI). (MRI) together with Coca-Cola’s Corporation for selecting and analyzing the environmental-friendliest vessel material (steel, glass and plastic) in terms of whether recycled vessels produced low effect or disposable[10]. At some point in the late1990s, the first Japan and later Korea and Australia increased their LCA work activity performing an important number of environmental researches. In contrast, LCA activity in the rest of Africa, Asia and Latin America was scarce. That trend has start to change, as activity in LCA is increasing in South Asia, Latin America and Africa. For example, The Brazilian government, recently launched a national project to development life cycle inventory data. LCA practitioners too also developing data and effect assessment methods, and applying them in both public and private sectors, in many of Latin American countries, such as Peru, Mexico, Chile, Colombia and Argentina . Recently in African LCA of network hosted LCA train workshop in which the participant start to develop a LS inventory information specifically applicable to every country[13]. LCA practice on concrete construction industry begun in the last decade, but only for environmental assessment of building and concrete construction materials selection. Therefore, LCA in the concrete construction industry is less developed now than in other industries, but appears to be developing quickly[14]. addition, LCA on structure is now a hot research theme in developed countries same, such as European Union, Japan and the North America [15].

5. An environmental assessment of steel structures (SC)

The steel and iron construction industry (SICI) is the world's widest of the energy consuming manufacturing construction industry with the widest share in the economy of the world's . In the steel and iron production over world, China takes the first place, and Japan, U.S. follow it. Turkey, with a 34.7 million tons production had a share of 2.1% of the total world production in 2013 (WSO, 2014) and ranked number eight among the steel-producing countries in the world. Meanwhile, in Turkey, Europe ranks number second after Germany (WSO, 2014). The steel and iron production is highly energy intensive and therefore it is associated highly with resource energy efficiency, conservation, and emissions reduction. Turkish SICI accounting for about 25%.of general energy use in industry of the manufacturing is therefore of particular interest in the same context of environmental effects. In this context, LCA provides a method for assessment of all environmental effects associated with a service or product. Through the LCA analysis, whole possible environmental loads of a service are ultimatelyclassified according to their contribution to a number of environmental effects, including ozone depletion potential, global warming potential and human toxicity. While LCA can be applied to compare the environmental effects of different products, it can be too applied to compare different production processes or to evaluate the sub-processes in a process of production between each anther process based LCA (Yilmz al., 2015). Hence, LCA can be used to determine the hotspots in LCA, i.e.

the phases causing greatest environmental harm, so that these can be aimed for improvements (Nicholas et al., 2000).

Several researches on LCA for steel and iron industry have been conducted around the world. Many of these researches are product based. For example, Sepia et al. (2002) carried out a LCA research to give a general review of the use of energy and materials, of the environmental impacts and emissions caused by the Finnish metal industry, and selected of the functional units was selected as one tone of product at the factory gate. In other study, Norgate et al. (2007) too carried out a product-based LCA, selecting 1 kg of refined metal as the functional units, and evaluated environmental effects of stainless steel and steel in terms of global warming potential (GWP), solid waste burden and gross energy requirement. In a comprehensive study, Tong pool et al. (2010) compared the proportional effects of different steel products (slab, hot-rolled, cold-rolled, hot-dipped galvanized, and electro-galvanized steels) in the categories of fossil fuels, global warming potential, minerals, Eco toxicity, carcinogens, respiratory inorganics and indicated that hot-dipped galvanized iron steel is with the highest effects. In a recent study, Get al. (2015) have developed a water footprint calculation model and calculated water footprint of steel from a LCA assessment perspective. They have indicated that the steel plant poses a serious risk to the environment of the water.

In the above mentioned researches, the same effect assessment methods that were used, but the discussion results are not still same comparable since they have different basis. Furthermore, the effect categories considered in these researches are not also comparable to each other. So, it is hard to led to a general conclusion out of these literature researches available. Moreover, to our knowledge, there is no research that considers the environmental effects of all processes and all product kinds concurrently. Thus, it is clean there is need to further investigate to clears the issues regarding the LCA for steel and iron industry. The differences in the inventory information used could result in different results. In most of the researches, country specific inventory data were used; therefore, the results reported are somewhat specific to their country. In fact, conducting's a LCA research country specific is basic importance in order to reach to the realistic results and conclusions representing country conditions.

6. An environmental assessment of wooden structures (WS)

Wood is a versatile raw material and is the only renewable building material. Wooden structures are usually characterized by having a mixture of different elements that together provide the best strength, thermal and acoustic insulation, moisture insulation, fire resistance, and long life. By increasing the proportion of timber in construction, the utilization Will decrease the utilization rates of other building materials, such as concrete, steel, and brick, can be reduced. Those building materials, which are not extracted from renewable raw materials, require a lot of energy to produce, and they increase carbon dioxide emissions. It should be noted that the European Union's long-term plan for a competitive economy with low carbon dioxide emissions is called the Road Map 2050. The main aim of this transformation will be energy saving (energy efficiency). An economy with low carbon dioxide emissions has a much greater need for renewable energy sources, energy-efficient building materials, energy-efficient designs, and energy-efficient transportation methods. In this context, the construction sector has both long and short term opportunities to reduce carbon dioxide emissions through the selection of materials with low environmental impact and through energy-efficient designs (energy-efficient designs / constructions). Increased use of wood products is part of the solution.

The past decade has witnessed a rapid development in the use of timber for the construction of buildings, and this is the result of the European Union's shift to standards based on use in construction legislation of member states. This now allows the construction of large buildings using wood-based systems. The manufacture of wood products requires the use of very little external energy, in addition to the energy from its own waste. It should be noted that about 80 percent of the energy consumed by carpentry factories in Sweden is biofuels from their production plans, such as sawdust, and about 20 percent of the energy they consume is electrical energy. The stages of the energy-consuming process are the drying stages of the timbers and the wooden beams. It is also the most energy-efficient stage that is used to power in drying places. When manufacturing other building materials, the starting point is always limited raw materials. Both extraction and industrialization require energy use, often in very large quantities and that is fossil fuel. When manufacturing cement, this process generates significant emissions of carbon dioxide, which is as it is the case during the steel industry operations. All building materials that are produced by following these processes have a large carbon footprint on the climate (that is, they increase carbon dioxide emissions and increase it in the air).

Measuring emissions of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases from production processes or activities helps the user to choose alternatives that have the least impact on climate and the environment. However, wood is less effective in this context, as carbon dioxide is stored in trees and emissions associated with harvesting, transporting and processing are fewer emissions compared to the amount of carbon dioxide stored.

Wood can replace other building materials in many buildings and constructions, and it does the same jobs. For example, in the standards of Swedish bridges (Bronormen), wooden bridges can be designed to perform the same functions and have the same life as in steel bridges and concrete bridges. Wood as a substitute material can mean a significant reduction in carbon dioxide emissions, which necessarily means significant climate benefits, when it replaces materials that require burning fossil fuels during their manufacture, which causes significant carbon dioxide emissions. One study showed that if wood products replace other building materials in buildings, there is an average replacement factor of about 1.6 tons of carbon dioxide per cubic meter of wood material, and this figure reaches 16 tons of carbon dioxide for the apartment that was Its foundation is on wooden foundations. With the significant saving in energy use and more environmentally friendly buildings and the environment, the production stage, and consequently the choice of wood, will become of great importance, and replacement will be important.

7. Results and Discussion

1. Results of an environmental assessment of steel reinforced concrete structures (SRC):-

Causes chimneys of cement plants release clinker dust, cement dust, smoke, carbon and sulfur oxides, nitrogen, hydrogen, lead and other gases and are the main component of environmental pollution as the spray of these oxides is attached to dust.

The cement industry is one of the industries that dangerously pollute the environment and cause acid rain, as well as causing health problems for its workers and the surrounding and neighboring residents of the factory as a result of cement dust and clinker and the gas emissions from this industry from

roasting the clinker where toxic gases are suspended particles suspended clinker dust as it emerges from the mouth of the factory and spread In his vicinity.

Some studies have proven to grind two thousand tons of clinker resulting in 40-50 tons of dust, knowing that the internationally permissible percentage is 15-25 mg per cubic meter, and the dust was less than 10 microns, the risk was capable because it is easily to inhalation and dust was less From 3 microns it receives severe health damage to the human being to end it and the condition is able to penetrate the respiratory defenses of humans and animals, and these studies have reported that the seminal dust from factories causes great environmental damage to the land, planting and seafloor while you are when these factories are near them, where a foamy layer forms Semi-gelatinous fish can destroy the environment in those seas.

As for the most important diseases that the cement industry causes to its workers in particular and to the health of the neighboring person in general are silicose disease, coughing, shortness of breath, asthma, emphysema, and the influence on the mucous membranes and their harassment and the influence on the nervous system in large part due to:

- 1) Dust: Inhalation of cement and clinker dust causes pulmonary fibrosis (silicose) as it is on the health and safety of the eyes and causes lung disease in general
- 2) Carbon monoxide: The high concentrations of it cause physiological changes in the human body, because it binds to blood 150-200 times faster than oxygen.
- 3) Sulfur oxides: They are on plants, humans and animals, and they are highly molested with mucous membranes and bronchi, and high concentrations of it cause suffocation.
- 4) Carbon monoxide gas: It causes the body to be deprived of oxygen when combined with hemoglobin in the blood
- 5) Hydrogen sulfide gas: It causes lethargy in thinking
- 6) Nitrogen oxides: Children have special health for children from 1 to 3 years, since they are polluted oxides
- 7) Lead: causes general epilepsy and weakness, causes stomach spasmodic pain and has a far-reaching impact on the brain and kidney disease.
- 8) Smoke: It is a smoke mist issued by the cement industry due to burning coal and oil derivatives in the oven, and it has an effect on the eyes, inflammation of the lungs and bronchi, and causes lung disease.
- 9) Volatile organic compounds.
- 10) Acid rain: it causes harassment of the nose, throat and eyes membranes and irritation of the respiratory membranes

The cement industry and the release of huge amounts of dust loaded with sulfur oxides, carbon and nitrogen, and the phosphate industry that emit dust loaded with uranium into the atmosphere are among the most dangerous causes of environmental pollution in general and are among the causes of acid rain, as these methods pose a threat to the environment, people and every living plant. It causes health diseases for humans, pollutes water sources, and interacts with minerals and pipes of water networks, causing erosion. Acid rain is a dangerous pollutant caused by cement and clinker dust, which is loaded with oxides, sulfur gases, nitrogen, and carbon oxides emitted from the nozzles of the cement factory chimneys, which are oxides and gases resulting from the combustion of materials, coal and other oil derivatives in the furnaces of these factories, and these rains are formed by the interaction of water vapor and oxygen in The atmosphere due to the presence of ultraviolet rays from the sun with raids containing sulfur dioxide and

hydrogen dioxide to give sulfur acid. Rivers, lakes, dams, and places from which groundwater sources are supplied and become acidic due to the decomposition of some toxic compounds to become free and see their way to the main sources of drinking water and their pollution

What increases the serious problem is the transfer of dust loaded with different oxide particles from the main source of pollution to another place that remains a fine mist in the air that moves according to the direction of the wind, because the sulfur dioxide suspended with dust interacts with the air when there is ultraviolet radiation and then turns into sulfur trioxide and unites With water vapor in the atmosphere to give the strong sulfuric acid. The acidity neutral pH is Ph.7, and the lower the acidity level of rain from the pH 5, the greater the risk of those acids. And it strips trees from its leaves and destroys its forests, which creates an imbalance and balance in nature and affects its beauty, because dense forest trees release into the atmosphere thousands of tons of oxygen and a platform thousands of tons of carbon dioxide harmful to the environment.

2. Results of an environmental assessment of steel and iron structures (SR):-

Carbon dioxide is produced in large quantities from the factories that produce steel, and since the steel industry relies heavily on iron, this gas is produced by reducing iron ores in the blast furnace, and sponge iron factories, in addition to that it results from the use of fossil fuel energy in the operations of Heating, it is worth noting that the coal used in energy production produces 90% of carbon dioxide.

Emission of nitrogen oxides are produced in factories where coal, electric arc furnaces, and heating furnaces are used, and since the iron and steel industry is highly dependent on high temperatures, it is difficult to avoid these oxides since nitrogen is present in the air.

Sulfur dioxide emissions Sulfur dioxide emissions are directly related to the combustion of oil in heating furnaces, and for the purposes of coal production. Climate change due to an increase in the proportion of greenhouse gases resulting from carbon dioxide gases produced during the steelmaking process. Slag forms slag and is defined as limestone impurities and iron ores that are produced from the smelting process of iron, as this process produces sulfur dioxide and volatile hydrogen sulfide, in addition to the slag that is used for construction purposes. Addressing pollution caused by the iron and steel industry, China is one of the most steel producing countries in the world, and as a result of the negative effects of this industry on the environment, new technologies have been used to reduce pollution, and these technologies depend on the reuse of energy from waste in the iron and coal industry. , Steel, and rolling process), these technologies are expected to save 220,000 tons annually.

3. Results of an environmental assessment of wooden structures (WS)

Building with wood has positive impacts on the climate. The way to create a climate neutral society is by saving energy and expanding the use of renewable energy sources.

For the construction and real estate sectors, this will have an impact on both the production and use stage. In new buildings, it is all about the choice of materials and the construction process having a low impact on the environment, and that the buildings are energy efficient. For existing buildings,

great emphasis will be placed on saving energy use, as the environmental impact of the construction phase has already occurred.

By 2050 we can estimate that about 80 percent of the existing buildings will be buildings already constructed today. Those buildings should be developed to be suitable for the future. So it is no accident that the greatest focus is on energy efficiency (energy saving). It should be noted that we are taking the example of new buildings because they provide a complete picture of the future building design system.

Historically, the operational phase of the building represented the largest use of energy during the life of the building, while the rate of energy use during the production phase is seen as a negligible proportion. With the emergence of new and tougher requirements for energy use in buildings, and in tougher cases buildings that use completely renewable energy (solar / wind energy), the use of energy during the production phase has become a matter of great importance.

Adapting the options of materials, designs and production processes to new conditions presents a major challenge for the construction sector. The great use of wood products and wood designs is an essential part of the solution, by storing carbon and the effects of its substitution.

Fig. 2. Embodied Carbon Dioxide Emissions for wood based products (blue) and other products (red).

8. Conclusions and Recommendations

1. Conclusions

1) concrete and cement are main components in construction today. The concrete has many environmental advantages, including longevity, durability, chemical inertia, heat storage capability and chemical inertia. In many of situations concrete is main to another materials such as steel and wood. But cement industrial is very energy intensive – cement is among the most energy-

intensive materials used in the construction industry and main contributor to CO₂ in atmosphere. To minimize environmental effect, we should try to decrease the concrete quantity used in constructions, use alternative concrete types (with silica fume and fly ash), and use this concrete wisely.

2) The study demonstrated that integrated steel and iron products have effects basically on respiratory Inorganics and global warming effect categories and it is recommended the facility giving the priority to those impact categories in investment planning stage for environmental impact reduction. In respiratory Inorganics impact category, the prior processes are liquid steel and hot rolling processes for finished products and liquid steel production process for semi-finished products. It would be beneficial to use effective dust collection methods to decrease the particulate emissions. In global warming effect category, LS (excluding LI consumption) and LI (excluding coke, sinter and pellet consumptions) production processes become prominent and carbon dioxide emission is strongly recommended to the method.

3) Nowadays, "green building" is good business. same a building material, wood many environmentally benefits that matter to communities across the country. it's the only main building material that is sustainable and renewable. Compared with steel and concrete, wood products help to increase a building's energy efficiency and minimize the energy consumed throughout the life of the product. Using wood too helps keep carbon out of the atmosphere, helping to mitigate climate change. Trees store carbon dioxide as they grow. After harvest, wood products continue to store much of this carbon. These benefits continue when wood is reclaimed to manufacture other industrial. Wood. It's a better method to structure.

2. Recommendations

It should be noted that the assessments presented in this research are based on some assumptions and also the accuracy of the data collected from the study plant, despite a close collaboration with the plant managers. In order to evaluate the influence of these parameters, several sensitivity analyses should be performed in future studies.

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